

REENGINEERING UNIVERSITY ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT THROUGH QR CODE SCANNING AND MOBILE APPLICATION: A SIMULATION-BASED APPROACH

Reema Choudhary^{*1}, Muhammad Nouman Maqsood², Ayesha Rashid³,
Nauman Riaz Choudhary⁴, Waqas Qayyum Butt⁵, Abrar Ali⁶

^{*1,2,4,5} Department of Software Engineering, University of Gujrat, Pakistan

^{3,4} Department of Computer Science, University of Gujrat, Pakistan

¹reema.choudhary@uog.edu.pk, ²noumanmaqsood636@gmail.com, ³ayesha.rashid@uog.edu.pk

⁴nauman.riaz@uog.edu.pk, ⁵butt09595@gmail.com, ⁶abrarali2551@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17439843>

Keywords

University attendance, QR-Code based attendance, Business Process Engineering, Simulation and Modeling

Article History

Received: 03 September 2025

Accepted: 13 October 2025

Published: 25 October 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Reema Choudhary

Abstract

Business process reengineering (BPR) is a procedure which basically focuses on the redesigning of already available core business processes to improve the quality, cost, and speed to get a better outcome. Student attendance system is a very important element which is required to measure the participation of students in a classroom. In many institutions, the student's attendance is taken very seriously and there is a rule of maintaining a certain percentage of attendance to be able to sit in final exams. Usually in most educational institutes, the attendance is taken manually using a physical register booklet. The problem with this method is that there is a risk of manipulation in this approach. Moreover, the attendance registers in which all the record is stored, could be lost, or stolen. There is another way to mark attendance directly on Learning Management System (LMS), but it is also not accurate because there is risk impersonation in it. So, taking this issue seriously, we made a simulation of this problem on AnyLogic using the available libraries and tried to give a solution to handle it. This paper aims to propose a system to provide the solution of these problems by taking students' attendance using a (Quick Response) QR code-based on mobile application. The paper discusses how the proposed system verifies student identity to eliminate false or duplicate attendance marking. In this proposed system, a QR code with the time stamp will be shown at lecturer presentation. Every lecturer will have a unique QR code for his/her subject and he will be responsible to display the QR code on the presentation screen. The students will only need to scan the displayed QR code using their mobile phone application to mark their attendance. The experimental results reveal a significant enhancement in process efficiency, as the proposed QR code-based attendance system successfully reduced the time required to record classroom attendance from nearly ten minutes using conventional methods to around three minutes with the automated mobile solution.

INTRODUCTION

Business Process Reengineering (BPR) is a control method to aim at improving the efficiency and

effectiveness of a corporation by fundamentally rethinking and redesigning of already available core

business processes. This approach involves analyzing existing process and identifying the problem for improvement to make according to the new technology for more efficient and accurate. The goal of BPR is to create a new business process using the existing process and it also requires the change in mindset. BPR can has a significant impact on organization, helping it to become a more agile, reduce cost, improve productivity, and improve customer satisfaction[1] [2].

It is a well-known fact that the students' attendance is an essential part of studies in any educational institute. In most universities, usually the students' attendance is taken by using a traditional method in which lecturer manually calls the roll number of students one by one and then makes a final report[3]. This attendance approach has several shortcomings, which include [4]:

- It takes time to call each student one at a time.
- Students can easily say "Present" when lecturer calls roll no. of their absent fellows.
- Moreover, some extra time is required to add attendance record into the database.

With the advancement of technology, there is need for more efficient and accurate solution which improve the student attendance system to track the absents students easily. Therefore, we suggested the solution to use the technology and implement the QR code-based attendance system instead of manually paperwork attendance.

We made a simulation of this problem on AnyLogic by using all the available libraries to understand the issue. We also created a state chart and a BPMN model of this problem to illustrate this problem. After that we also made a proper recommended solution simulation for demonstrate the benefits of QR code-based attendance system. This simulation allows the teacher to visualize the impact of QR code-based attendance system.

There are several digital attendance systems which are implemented in different organizations and institutions. But they also have some drawbacks which are discussed below:

- Some systems are to be only accessible via a computer.

- Some systems are very costly to be implemented, so small organizations with limited budgets can't afford such systems.
- Some systems require additional investment in technology upgrades.
- Some systems are difficult to understand and operate, requiring additional training and support.

Therefore, the main objective of "QR Code Attendance System" is to eliminate all the problems related to students' attendance. Basically, in this system, there will be a mobile application which will be used to generate a unique QR code for each subject. Each lecturer of a particular subject will be allotted with a personal QR code of his/her subject. The lecturer will show the QR code in presentation screen (LED) for a particular time.

Moreover, the mobile application will also be used by students to scan that QR code to mark their attendance in a selected time which allotted from lecturer. The app will automatically mark the attendance of every student for currently particular session. Some studies focuses on modeling a barcode-based attendance system using flowcharts, UML diagrams, and ER models. It simulates student attendance tracking through a web application, ensuring effective management of attendance in educational institutions [5].

There will be a time limit within which the students will need to scan QR code. After this time limit, QR code will be removed from the presentation screen of lecturer and any remaining student will no longer be able to mark his/her attendance. After the time limit when one user scans the QR code will be sent to the system's server where attendance will be evaluated. Then, the attendance report will be generated in excel files for further use. The proposed system will have several advantages, including:

- It will provide accurate and efficient attendance record.
- It will generate quick results because it is automatic.
- It will take less time as compared to the manual approach.
- It will be user friendly because it's very easy to use.

Material and Methods: To develop the proposed QR Code based attendance system, a proper methodology has been followed:

Figure 1: Overview of Methodology

2.1 Data Collection:

To introduce a new system, there was a need to study all the already existing systems to identify all the loopholes and problems so that the redesigned system can become more efficient and accurate. Therefore, we conducted a study to know whether the students and the lecturer at university really wants this new proposed system or they are satisfied with the current system and don't want to adopt the digital approach. This study was conducted at the University of Gujrat. The participants targeted in this research were the students and the lecturers at university. The method we used to gather information was using a questionnaire.

Questionnaire is a set of questions which can be used to gather information for research purposes. It is the most used way of collecting data regarding any field. Its main aim is to gather relevant information in the most reliable and accurate way[4] [7].

So, our questionnaire had 12 questions related to the current system and our proposed digital attendance

system. The questions were aimed at understanding their current experiences with the existing system, their views on the proposed new system, and what changes they would like to see in the new system. We received almost 130 responses on this questionnaire from which 100 respondents were students and the remaining 30 respondents were the lecturers who teaches different subjects at university. The collected data was then reviewed and analyzed to interpret and identify specific problems faced by the targeted participants in the attendance module. The results of the study have been analyzed using descriptive facts and inferential information. The descriptive statistics provided a general overview of the participants' responses, even as inferential records allowed us to determine if there has been a widespread difference among the perspectives of the students and the lecturers. Results of data are given in Table 1(Lecturer) and Table 2(Students)[5].

Options	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6
Strongly Agree	20	18	25	28	19	26
Agree	6	4	2		5	4
Neutral	4	5	3	2	3	
Disagree		3			3	
Strongly Disagree						

Table 1. Collected data results from the 30 university lecturers.

Options	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6
Strongly Agree	60	66	81	79	82	62
Agree	9	17	16	10	15	10
Neutral	20	12	3	4	3	28
Disagree	8	5		7		
Strongly Disagree	3					

Table 2. Collected data results from the 100 university students.

The results showed that most of the students and lecturers were supportive of the new proposed system and believed that it would improve the current system's efficiency and accuracy. They expressed that they would welcome the digital approach as it would make their work easier and more convenient. However, some participants had concerns about the

security of the information that would be stored in the new system.

Below is the table 3 which shows the details of the responses we received on our Questionnaire:

Description	Attributes	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	60	45
	Female	70	55
Age of Respondents	20-25	80	60
	30-35	20	17
	36-40	24	20
	Above 40	6	3
Educational Qualification	BSc/MSc	70	58
	MPhil	25	15
	PhD	35	27
Grades of Employee	Grade-18	18	60
	Grade-19	12	40

Table 3. Details of the participant of our Survey.

2.2 Flowchart:

Due to the complexity of software applications in the recent years, users have given more emphasis on object-oriented design technique than usual for decreasing cost and increasing the usability of their software. But this new practice of item-oriented surroundings in the designing and implementation of software program brings new issues inside the testing phase of packages. This takes place due to the encapsulation, inheritance, polymorphism, and dynamic binding of object-oriented programming approach. In order to test the object interaction, alot

of researchers have introduced several techniques which are based on UML Diagrams. (flow chart, use-cases, and sequence)[6].

A flowchart is a type of diagram which consists of circular shapes, quadrilaterals, and arrows. The circular shape classes contain terminator and connection (oval and circle respectively). The quadrilateral classes contain processes, data, and decisions (rectangle, parallelogram, and diamond respectively). It is used to represent a workflow or process[7].

Figure 2: Flow chart diagram of QR-Code based Attendance System
The description of our proposed system’s flow chart is given below:

Activity	Description
Start	The process is starting from start.
Already Register	When the process starts, there is a decision step of “Already Register”. If the user is already registered on the system, then he/she will be directed towards “Generate QR-Code” step or “Scan QR-code” step according to your positions.
Fill all credentials	But if the user is not registered, then he/she will be redirected to the step of “Fill all credentials” where user will be required to fill all the necessary details to complete registration.
Check Accuracy	After this, next step is “Check Accuracy” where the system will check that the user entered correct details or invalid details. If the details are wrong, then user will be return to previous step of “Fill all credentials”.
Generate QR-Code and Show QR-Code on screen	Now, as we know that there are two actors in our system including student and lecturer. So, the next step is directed in two different directions based on the actor. If the correct credentials are entered by lecturer, then the next step is “Generate QR-Code” where lecturer will need to generate a QR code using the smartphone application. And then, the next step is “Show QR-Code on screen” where lecturer will show the generated QR code on the presentation screen so that students can mark attendance.
Disappear QR-Code	After some time, the lecturer will remove the QR code from the screen in “Disappear QR-Code” step. After this, the system will be directed to “Stop” from lecturer’s side.
Code Scanning	On the other hand, students will be directed to a next step of “Code Scanning”. In this step, student will scan the QR code using app.
Check Result	Next step is “Check Result” where system will check whether the scan was successful or not. If result is bad, then the student will again need to scan the code.
Store attendance in DB	On the other hand, if the result is good, then system will store the attendance of student in Database. This step is named as “Store attendance in DB” on the flowchart.
Stop	After the whole process is done, the system will be stopped.

Table 4. Details of all flow chart activities

2.3 Use Cases:

Use case diagram was first introduced by Ivar Jacobson in 1986. It is a type of diagram which is used in system analysis for the identification, interpretation, and arrangement of requirements[8].

Use case diagram is a graphical depiction of the interplay the various factors of gadget. on this context the time period “machine” refers to something being evolved. Use case diagram are hired in Unified Modeling Language (UML),In our system, Students

and Lecturers are primary actors and Database is secondary actor[9].

The description of our system’s use cases is given below:

Figure 3: Use case diagram of students for QR-Code based Attendance System

Use Case Description

Use Cases are completed successfully when a certain goal is achieved and justified. Use Case description also have possible enhancements in this sequence. Like unique alternative sequences which may justify the goal, as well as the ones sequences which can also cause failure in pleasurable the service in situations like first-rate conduct and mistakes handling.[10]

Use Case ID: 01

Use Case: Register Account

Primary Actor: Students

Secondary Actor: Database

Description:

Student will register a new account in the app. To do this, they will need to fill the required details like name, roll number and a password. Then, the system will perform a verification to check whether the submitted credentials are correct or not. If the student missed something during inputting details, then system will ask him/her to submit missing details again. Otherwise, him/her account will be created successfully.

Actor	System
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> System will restrict the student that for account registration, student must input all the credentials on the register interface in app.

<p>2. Student will create his/her account by using name, roll number and password.</p>	<p>3. System will accept student's account information and verify with database if the name and roll number is valid then successfully account registered else student will need to enter details again.</p>
--	--

Pre-Condition:

N/A.

Post Condition:

Scan QR-Code

Use Case ID: 02

Use Case: Scan QR-Code

Primary Actor: Students

Secondary Actor: Database

Description:

After registration, student will scan the QR Code to mark his/her attendance. Then, the system will verify the scan. If any error occurs during scanning, the student will again need to scan the QR code. Once verification is done, the system will save the attendance report in the Database for further use.

Actor	System
<p>1. Student will scan the QR Code to mark attendance.</p>	<p>2. System will do verification of scanning whether it was successful or not. If not, then student will re-scan the code until system verification is done.</p> <p>3. System will save the attendance in Database.</p>

Pre-Condition:

Students register an account.

Post Condition:

N/A

Figure 4: Use case diagram of Lecturers for QR-Code based Attendance System

Use Case Description

Use Case ID: 03

Use Case: Register Account

Primary Actor: Lecturer

Secondary Actor: Database

Description:

Lecturer will need to register an account in the application. For this, he/she will need to fill the required details like personal name, roll number and a password. Then, the system will perform a verification to check whether the submitted credentials are correct or not. If the lecturer misses something during inputting details, then system ask lecturer to submit missing details again. Otherwise, him/her account will be created successfully.

Actor	System
2. Lecturer will create account by entering name, ID, and password.	1. System will restrict the lecturer that to register an account, lecturer must input all the credentials on the register interface in app. 3. System will accept lecturer's account information and verify with database if the name and roll number entered is valid then account will be registered in the database otherwise lecturer will need to enter details again.

Pre-Condition:

N/A

Post Condition:

Generate QR-Code

Use Case ID: 04

Use Case: Generate QR-Code

Primary Actor: Lecturer

Secondary Actor: Database

Description:

The lecturer will generate a QR code using the application. Then, he will show the generated code on the presentation screen so that the students can scan it to mark their attendance.

Actor	System
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lecturer generates a QR code. 2. Then shows this QR code on the screen. 	

Pre-Condition:

Lecturers register an account.

Post Condition:

N/A

2.4 Sequence Diagram:

The sequence diagram is used to represent the interactions among objects in a sequential order that the ones interactions occur. As in class diagram,

builders usually assume that series diagrams have been supposed best for them. but, an business enterprise's enterprise group of workers can discover series diagrams useful to talk how the business presently works through showing how diverse enterprise items engage[11].

The overall sequence diagram of QR-Code based attendance system is given below:

Figure 5: Sequence diagram of QR-Code based Attendance System

First of all, the process will start from lecturers and students' side, and they will need to register an account in the application, and he/she will send the message to App class and the App class will return the message again that fill all required credentials. When lecturers and students enter all credentials than App class access the Database class Then, the Database class will perform a verification to check whether the submitted credentials are correct or not. If the inputting details will be correct, then Database class will return the successfully registered message to the App class. Otherwise, the Invalid information, try again message will return to the App class. The whole steps will do until the registered account message will wrong.

Second, Lecturer will need to generate the qr code, and he/she will send the message to App class and again App class will return the response message for fill all required credentials. Once the lecturers will fill all credentials than App will generate the code.

After that the lecturer will show the QR-Code on presentation screen and the students will start his/her process and for using the mobile app they access the LED for scanning code if the scanning code process completed with successfully than attendance will be saved on database of that particular student. Otherwise, App class will show the Invalid message on screen than the lecturer will disappear the code from presentation screen and process will be closed(terminated).

2.5 Simulation:

Shannon (1975) said that Simulation is a technique of designing an exact model of a real system and doing experiments with this model to understand the behavior of the system or to evaluate different strategies for the working of the system[12] [15].

Simulation which is created in the architecture and design stage is a cost effective replacement to the actual implementation and execution of real system. [13].

It is a powerful and authentic tool if understood and used properly. It is one of the most widely used problem-solving methodology for the solution of various real-life problems[14].

2.5.1. Problem Simulation:

To make the simulation of the current system, we used the information gathered from the participants' responses. We analyzed their feedback to identify the problems and limitations of the existing system. This helped us to understand the areas that needed improvement in the new system. The simulation allowed us to visualize the problems and to test different solutions to see which ones worked best.

In our case, we made simulation model of problem in AnyLogic Simulation environment. AnyLogic is a simulation software tool which can be used to create a virtual environment of complex systems with different strategies. It also enables users to create a highly customized based on the features of the modeled system. A brief description of AnyLogic diagram of our problem simulation model is given below:

Before Run

Figure 6.1: AnyLogic simulation logic of current system

After Run

Figure 6.2: AnyLogic simulation logic of current system

Title	Description
studentSource and lecturerSource	The sources including students and lecturers are randomly generated from classrooms or offices respectively. Students will be generated from studentSource and the lecturers will be generated by lecturerSource.
tchrTimeMeasureStart	The “tchrTimeMeasureStart” is used to measure the starting time of marking attendance. We are only measuring the lecturers time because the whole attendance work is done by lecturers which includes firstly mark attendance on papers than saved attendance on server.
goingToClass and goingToClassRoom	The student source will go to the corresponding classroom passing through “goingToClass” point. And the lecturer will go to the class via “goingToClassRoom” point.
Queue	In case of student’s source, there is a “queue” function applied which will allow students to make a queue and enter the classroom on first come first served basis.
markAttendance	This is showing that lecturer mark attendance of students by calling their roll numbers.
tchrTimeMeasureEnd	The “tcheTimeMeasureEnd” calculate the end time when the lecturer has done the mark attendance work and this action conclude the distribution time for marking attendance.
Learning	A “learning” point shows that students will learn their respective subject.
sitOnChair	The point of “SitOnChair” indicates that the lecturer will sit on chair after waiting.
Teaching	The lecturer will start teaching at this point.
leaveTheClass	After the lecture ends, the students will leave the classroom.

studentSink and teacherSink	After all the process, the end time will be measured by using “stdTimeMeasureEnd” and then both sources will be sinked into their corresponding sink points as shown in above diagram.
Schedule	There is a schedule parameter added in this simulation. In Pic 1, it is showing that there is no lecturer and student in class and the teacher will come in next 48.04 seconds while the students will come in 48.04 seconds. On the other hand, Pic 2(After Run) indicates there is 1 lecturer and 20 current students in the classroom. Current class attendance is shown below:

Table 5. Details of simulation logic of current system

id	att result
1	Absent
2	Absent
3	Absent
4	Present
5	Present
6	Present
7	Present
8	Present
9	Present
10	Present
11	Present
12	Present
13	Present
14	Present
15	Present
16	Present
17	Present
18	Present
19	Present
20	Present
21	Present
22	Present
23	Present
24	Present
25	Present
26	Present
27	Absent
28	Absent
29	Absent
30	Absent
31	Absent
32	Absent

This report is showing that there are 23 present students in the class but in reality, the students are only 20. It means that the attendance is done false because some students have marked attendance of their absent fellows too.

2.5.2. Solution Simulation

After the experiment of problem simulation, we then build a simulation of our proposed digital attendance

system. It was also made on AnyLogic tool. A brief description of our solution simulation model is given below:

Before Run

Figure 7.1: AnyLogic simulation logic of future QR-Code based attendance system

After Run

Figure 7.2: AnyLogic simulation logic of future QR-Code based attendance system

Title	Description
Sources	The students will be generated from studentSource and the lecturers will be generated from lecturerSource.
stdTimeMeasureStart	The “stdTimeMeasureStart” measures the start time for each stream of student source. We are only measuring the students time because the whole attendance work is done by students which includes app registration, code scanning etc.
goingToClass and goingToClassRoom	The student source will go to the corresponding classroom passing through “goingToClass” point. And the lecturer will go to the class via “goingToClassRoom” parameter.
Queue	For students, there is a “queue” function applied which will allow them to make a queue and enter the classroom on first come first served manner.
showingQR_Code	The lecturer will show the attendance QR code on the presentation screen in the classroom.
scanCodeAnd MarkAttOnServer	Here the students will scan the QR code to mark their attendance on the server.

moveToBoard	Then, the lecturer will wait for a particular time.
stdTimeMeasureEnd	The “stdTimeMeasureEnd” calculate the end time when the students have marked the attendance by scanning QR-Code on presentation screen and this action conclude the distribution time for marking attendance.
sitOnSeat	After scanning code, students will go back to their seats.
Teaching	Then, the teacher will start teaching students.
Sink	At the end, the students and teachers will sink on studentSink and teacherSink respectively.
Schedule	There is a schedule parameter added in this simulation. In Pic 1, it is showing that there is no lecturer and student in class and the teacher will come in next 56.01 seconds while the students will come in 61.01 seconds. On the other hand, Pic 2(After Run) indicates there is 1 lecturer and 12 current students in the classroom. Current class attendance is shown below:

Table 6. Details of simulation logic of future QR-Code based attendance system

id	att result
1	Present
2	Present
3	Present
4	Present
5	Present
6	Present
7	Present
8	Present
9	Present
10	Present
11	Present
12	Present
13	Absent
14	Absent
15	Absent
16	Absent
17	Absent
18	Absent
19	Absent
20	Absent
21	Absent
22	Absent
23	Absent
24	Absent
25	Absent
26	Absent
27	Absent
28	Absent
29	Absent
30	Absent
31	Absent
32	Absent

This attendance report is shows that there are exactly 12 present students in the class. It means that this approach of marking attendance is removing the error of false attendances.

State charts

UML state chart is an object-based variant of classical state chart. A state chart contains states and transitions of a workflow. State charts extend finite nation machines with composite states to describe any complicated behavior[15].

2.6.1. TEACHER STATE CHART - Existing System:

In the case of existing attendance approach, all the work is done by teacher therefore the state chart of teacher is created which is explained below:

Figure 8: State chart of current system

State	Description
idle state	<p>From the above chart, it is clear that the very first state of system is “idle”. At this state, the university will be opened but lecturer and students will not be in the classroom to conduct lecture. This state chart shows the only lecturer’s state because this state chart is for current manual attendance system in which mostly attendance work is the responsibility of lecturer.</p> <p>After this state, there are three possibilities based on time.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First, the system is waiting for class schedule to start. The system is active and doesn’t perform any action. When the schedule will start the system transition to the next state which is “goingToClass”. 2. If the time of lecture is already passed, then the system will return to the idle state. 3. If the closing time of university has arrived i.e., 5 pm, then the system will be ended which is its final state.
goingToClass	The next state is “goingToClass”. At this state, lecturer will move towards the classroom.
markAttendance	Once again, there is a time condition. If the lecture time is remaining, then the lecturer will mark attendance of students manually on register or pages. This state is shown as “markAttendance” in the chart.
teachingState	In this state, the lecturer will start teaching students if there is time remaining for lecture. After teaching, if the lecture time is passed, then teacher will go back to his office. At this time, the system will be at “goBackoffice” state.
goBackOffice	But if there is no time left for lecture, then the teacher will leave the class and go back to office. This is “goBackoffice” state. And then the system will return to its idle state if university is still open.
finalState	But if the University closing time has reached, the system will be transferred to end state.

Table 7. Details of state chart of current system

2.6.2. STUDENTS STATE CHART - New System:

In our new system, the maximum work is done by students. Therefore, we only explained student state in this case.

Figure 9: State chart of future QR-Code based attendance system

State	Description
idleState	<p>From the above chart, it is clear that the very first state of system is “idle”. At this state, the university will be opened but lecturer and students will not be in the classroom to conduct lecture. This state chart shows the only student’s state because this state chart is for future QR-Code based attendance system in which mostly attendance work is the responsibility of students.</p> <p>After this state, there are three possibilities based on time.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First, the system is waiting for class schedule to start. The system is active and doesn’t perform any action. When the schedule will start the system transition to the next state which is “goingToClass”. 2. If the time of lecture is already passed, then the system will return to the idle state.

	3. If the closing time of university has arrived i.e., 5 pm, then the system will be ended which is its final state.
goingToClass	The next state is “goingToClass”. At this state, lecturer will move towards the classroom.
scanAtt_Code	Once the students arrive in the class, they scan the QR-code displayed on the presentation screen and for the time they can scan it, but one student can scan only for yourself. This triggers the transition to the next state. Once again, there is a condition if the scan code status will be successful then the system move the next state which is att_Saved otherwise the system return to previous state scanAtt_Code.
att_Saved	Upon scanning the QR-Code, the system automatically saves the attendance of the students in server. This indicates the students present in the class.
Studing	But if there is no time left for lecture, then the students will leave the class. If time is more than the students will sit on their and start learning. This system remains in this state until the lecture time has not ended that already set on schedule. And then the system will return to its idle state if university is still open.
finalState	But if the University closing time has reached, the system will be transferred to end state.

Table 8. Details of state chart of future QR-Code based attendance system

2.6 Business Process Model and Notations (BPMN):

BPMN, which stands for Business Process Model and Notation, is a visual representation of a business process. It provides a standardized way to graphically show how tasks and events in a business process are connected, helping to make the process more understandable. BPMN became first brought in 2004 by the enterprise process Modeling Initiative [16].

The BPMN of the existing attendance system is described below:

BPMN → Existing System

Figure 10: BPMN model of current system

In this case, the pool in the BPMN Diagram is representing “UNIVERSITY_ATTENDANCE”, therefore the participant is “UNIVERSITY_ATTENDANCE”. And the process

is partitioned to illustrate which participants are doing which activities within the system. Therefore, each lane represents a function.

Activity	Description
goToClass	So, the process is starting from the “Student” lane. The first activity is “goToClass” which indicates that students will go to the classroom.
goToClass	On the other hand, in “Teacher” lane, there is a “Timer” condition of i.e., 9 a.m. When this time reaches, the activity will start which is “goToClass”. It shows that teacher will go to the classroom at this time.
markAttendance	On the student’s side, there is a conditional intermediate of “askingForAttendanceMark”. And there is a “Exclusive” gateway in teacher lane. It means that the student will ask for attendance marking then the next activity will occur in both lanes which is “markAttendance”. In this activity, teacher will mark the attendance of students by calling their roll numbers.
attendanceCompleted	Then, there is an end event in student’s lane which is a message of “markAttendanceCompleted”. When the attendance will be completed, it will be sent to teacher lane as showing in above BPMN Diagram with an intermediate message of “attendanceCompleted”.
teachAndLeaveClass	In teacher lane, the next activity is “taught” which indicates that the teacher will give lecture to students. And then there is an activity of “leaveClass” in which the teacher will leave the classroom and go back to office. After this, the process will end.

Table 9. Details of BPMN model of current system

2.7.1. BPMN → New System

The BPMN diagram of our proposed attendance system is described below:

Figure 11: BPMN model of future QR-Code based attendance system

In this case, the participant is three lanes including teachers, students, and “UNIVERSITY_ATTENDANCE_SYSTEM” as scanner_app. shown in the pool. And the process is partitioned into

Activity	Description
goToClass	Here, the process is starting from the “Students” lane. The first activity is “goToClass” which indicates that students will go to the classroom. While on the teachers’ side, there is a timer of like i.e., 9 am. When this timer reaches, the teacher will also go to the classroom.
teachAndShow Attendance_QRCode	The next activity is “taught” which shows that the teacher will give lecture to the students. After this, the next step is “showAttendance_QRCode” in which the teacher will show the QR code on the presentation screen and will send the signal toward students for scanning code.
scanQR_Code	In student’s lane, there is a signal condition of “QR code available”. So, when teacher show QR code, this condition will meet, and the next activity will be “scanQR_Code” where students will scan QR code to mark their attendance.
scanner_App	After scanning, there is a multiple intermediate event in “Scanner_App” lane which have three different outcomes. If the scan is not done correctly then the process will return back to “scanQR_Code”.

leaveTheClass	But if the scan is successfully done, the students will leave the class and the process will end.
disAppearAttendance QR-Code	And if the timer condition meets, the process will be directed to “disAppearAttendance_QRCode” in teachers’ lane where lecturer will remove the QR code from the screen. After this activity, the lecturer will also leave the classroom and the whole process will finally end.

Table 10. Details of BPMN model of future QR-Code based attendance system.

1) Theory/Calculation:

The approach of BPR can be applied to various processes within an organization, including student attendance. Student attendance is a crucial aspect of education as it has a direct impact on a student's academic performance. In the context of student attendance, BPR could be performed by analyzing the current process for recording and tracking student attendance, identifying all the problems, and then designing a new process that makes it more efficient. This can be achieved by using technology, like online attendance systems or smartphone apps, which can automate the manual process and provide real-time data. The goal of BPR in student attendance would be to improve accuracy and to reduce burden faced by administration in student attendance. By automating the attendance-taking process, BPR can free teachers from spending extra time with their students and providing individual help. This can even help students to improve their overall academic performance.

There are several attendance systems developed by different organizations and educational institutes using punch cards, fingerprint systems, barcodes, and RFID. These are also not efficient as they sometimes provide incorrect information to the users. Therefore, we will be using BPR technique to develop a more reliable system to manage students’ attendance[17].

2) Results:

4.1 The Current and Future condition of attendance system:

The use of technology in education has greatly increased in the recent years leading the new way of recording the students’ attendance. One such method is QR code-based attendance system. In most cases, the current attendance system is done using a manual system like marking attendance on pages or registers and then upload records on server (Database). While future condition refers to attendance approach using the QR code-based attendance system. The result of exploration of both conditions are supplied in Table 11[18].

Focus	Current System condition	Future Condition System
Process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preparation 2. Take attendance forms 3. Mark attendance 4. Returning or manage attendance 5. Upload attendance on server manually 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. App registration 2. Mark attendance through scanning 3. Upload attendance on server automatically

Resources	Actors who play a role in attendance activities are: 1. Academic body of workers 2. Lecturer 3. Students	Actors who play a role in attendance activities are: 1. Academic body of workers 2. Lecturer 3. Students 4. Attendance App (Scanner App)
Technology	The current manual system uses papers.	The future QR code-based attendance system uses code scanner system as a medium for attendance.
Attendance Time	In before manual attendance system, the time taken by a teacher for taking attendance is almost 606 seconds which is almost equal to 10.11 Minutes as show in Figure 12.1.	In after QR code attendance system this attendance time almost reduce to 341.4 second which is approximately equal to 5.69 Minutes and there is no teacher effort there as well as show in figure 12.2.

Table 11. Comparison between current(manual) and future(QR-Code based) attendance system

Figure 12.1: Attendance time measurement of current system

Figure 12.2: Attendance time measurement of new system

4.2 Resources Explanation:

In current manual attendance system, the Academic staff is responsible for generating the attendance sheets and lecturer takes the sheets to mark the attendance but in advanced QR code-based attendance system, the academic staff will be responsible for developing the Scanner App for attendance and for future updates. The Lecturer will be responsible for showing the QR code on presentation screen for a particular time. The students will be responsible to scan the code through Scanner app to mark their present. During the scanning, the app will mark attendance on backend server one by one of students.

4.2.1. Mobile Application:

This process includes the development of a mobile application which will be used to generate QR Codes. QR codes can hide any type of information including numeric and alphanumeric. A QR code image consists of some black and white rows and columns. It is introduced to be read by smartphone to decode the hidden information[19]. Moreover, our smartphone application will also have a function by using which students will be able to scan the QR Code to mark their attendance. More details regarding this application are given below:

Figure 13: Mobile Application Working Structure

Interface Design:

The attendance app has different interfaces, but main interfaces are discussed in the case study. Firstly, the user will install the app in his/her mobile and start with the registration interface and the user fill all required credentials and click on signup button. If the required information will be accurate who user will enter then his/her account will be register successfully as show in Figure 14.2. And the logout option will not exit in the app because the other user doesn't create his/her account on same mobile. After that the user will see the home page of app where his image and username will be show and the user will be scanning the code that show on the presentation screen from the lecturer side. If the user will scan code by using attendance app, then the present of that user will be marked.

Figure 14.1

Figure 14.2

Figure 14.3

Figure 14.1: Sign up interface of new attendance app

Figure 14.2: Home Page interface of new attendance app

Figure 14.3: QR-Code based interface of new attendance app

4.2.2. Result:

The result of experimental survey indicates a clear preference for the QR-Code based attendance system over the traditional manual system. A staggering 90% of students reported a preference for the QR-Code based attendance system, while only 10% indicated a preference for the manual. The superiority of the QR-Code based attendance system lies in its accuracy and efficiency. With the QR-Code system, attendance can be taken quickly and with 100% accuracy, eliminating

the need for manual recording and reducing the risk of errors. The saved attendance data is easily processed, allowing for the generation of reports, and providing easy accessibility to both students and lecturers. The survey results reinforce the conclusion that the QR-Code based attendance system offers numerous benefits over the manual process, making it the ideal choice for organization seeking to improve their attendance management system.

3) Discussion:

The purpose of this section is to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the QR code-based attendance system, focusing on its strengths and limitations. Until now, we explained the problems of existing system and briefly discussed the importance of a digital system to handle all the shortcomings. We also described the experiments and results of the new

system. The feedback of the targeted users is collected and used to interpret the expected outcomes. Their response also helped us in understanding the mindsets of nowadays education community. For the time being, our proposed system is not yet launched and not in working. It is just a real-world idea proposed by us. This system offers several advantages over traditional attendance methods, like paper sign-in sheets or manual tallying.

However, there are also some challenges associated with a QR code-based attendance system. For example, it may not work in areas with poor internet connectivity, and employees or students may not have access to a smartphone or tablet to scan the code. In such cases, alternative methods of recording attendance may be needed.

In conclusion, a QR code-based attendance system is a convenient and efficient way to track attendance, but it's far important to don't forget the potential challenges and obstacles earlier than implementing it.

4) Conclusions:

In this paper, a "QR Code Based Attendance System" has been proposed which replaces the traditional manual process of managing attendance which is currently used. Among all the previously introduced attendance systems, the QR code-based system is most efficient and reliable which provides accurate information in real time. The proposed system can be implemented in any educational institution or in any other organization where there is a need to improve the attendance module. Based on the results of our questionnaire and experiments, it is concluded that many respondents agree with the implementation of new proposed attendance system. The study shows that the system will reduce the additional work of administration and will also save a lot of time. Moreover, the lecturers will no longer have to record students' attendance manually on papers. We hope that this system will receive a very positive response from all the relevant departments. This system has been introduced with expected results and it can still be improved by adding more useful features in future. Like the security of the system can be enhanced further to make the working of system more reliable. Any new features can also be added within the passage of time according to the needs of users. So, in short, this system is an innovation in the traditional

attendance system and uses the available technology to make the difficult tasks much easier than before.

References:

- [1] R. D. Pasaribu, G. Anggadwita, R. Hendayani, R. B. Kotjoprayudi, and D. I. N. Apiani, "Implementation of business process reengineering (BPR): Case study of official trip procedures in higher education institutions," *JTEM*, vol. 14, no. 3, p. 622, July 2021, doi: 10.3926/jiem.3403.
- [2] R. Choudhary and N. Riaz, "A business process re-engineering approach to transform business process simulation to BPMN model," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 18, no. 3, p. e0277217, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0277217.
- [3] R. A. Sheikh, R. Al-Assami, M. Albahr, and M. A. Suhaibani, "DEVELOPING AND IMPLEMENTING A BARCODE BASED STUDENT ATTENDANCE SYSTEM," vol. 06, no. 1, 2019.
- [3] T. Sutabri, P. Pamungkur, A. Kurniawan, and R. E. Saragih, "Automatic Attendance System for University Student Using Face Recognition Based on Deep Learning," *IJMLC*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 668-674, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.18178/ijmlc.2019.9.5.856.
- [5] O. Sarjiyus, M. Hamidu, and M. Audu, "Simulation of Barcode Based Students' Examination Attendance System," *Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 195-209.
- [6] H. Taherdoost, "Validity and Reliability of the Research Instrument; How to Test the Validation of a Questionnaire/Survey in a Research," *SSRN Journal*, 2016, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3205040.
- [7] Reema Choudhary, Adrees Shahbaz, Ali Usman, Nauman Riaz Chaudhry, Muhammad Hanan Haider, and Muhammad Suhail, "ENHANCING INMATE MEETING PROCESSES: A SIMULATION-DRIVEN BUSINESS PROCESS ENGINEERING APPROACH," *IJCIS*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 1781-1789, June 2024.

- [8] D. Rahmawati, F. W. Putro, and A. Y. Wicaksono, "Student Attendance System using QR Codes (Case Study: Institut Teknologi Telkom Surabaya)".
- [9] "[No title found]," in *2008 16th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communications*, Chennai, India: IEEE, 2008.
- [8] C. Carton, A. Lemaitre, and B. Couasnon, "Fusion of Statistical and Structural Information for Flowchart Recognition," in *2013 12th International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition*, Washington, DC, USA, Aug. 2013, pp. 1210-1214. doi: 10.1109/ICDAR.2013.245.
- [11] A. Y. Aleryani, "Comparative Study between Data Flow Diagram and Use Case Diagram," vol. 6, no. 3, 2016.
- [12] B. Geppert and K. Schmid, "Co-located with the IEEE Joint International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE02)".
- [13] "<http://www.ibm.com/developerworks/rational/library/3101.html>".
- [14] R. G. Ingalls, "INTRODUCTION TO SIMULATION".
- [15] F. Farooq, R. Choudhary, H. Batool, N. R. Choudhary, and M. Ehsan, "REDUCING WAITING TIME AND IMPROVING PATIENT FLOW IN PUBLIC SECTOR HOSPITALS USING BUSINESS PROCESS ENGINEERING AND SIMULATION," *Pakistan Journal of Science*, vol. 76, no. 01, Art. no. 01, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.57041/pjs.v76i01.1133.
- [16] A. Egyed and D. Wile, "Statechart simulator for modeling architectural dynamics," in *Proceedings Working IEEE/IFIP Conference on Software Architecture*, Amsterdam, Netherlands: IEEE Comput. Soc, 2001, pp. 87-96. doi: 10.1109/WICSA.2001.948413.
- [17] J. Banks, "1999: INTRODUCTION TO SIMULATION".
- [18] M. Chinosi and A. Trombetta, "BPMN: An introduction to the standard," *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 124-134, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.csi.2011.06.002.
- [19] Henan University of Technology *et al.*, "QR Code Based Smart Attendance System," *IJSBT*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1-10, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.21742/ijsbt.2017.5.1.01.
- [20] E. Sulistiyani, A. H. N. Ali, and H. M. Astuti, "Change Management Strategies to Implement A Fingerprint Based Attendance System in Information Systems Department Using ADKAR Model," *ATCSJ*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 22-29, Sept. 2020, doi: 10.33086/atcsj.v3i1.1675.
- [21] Z. Deineko, S. Sotnik, and V. Lyashenko, "Usage and Application Prospects QR Codes," vol. 6, no. 7, 2022.

